

BEHAVIOR OF SANDWICH BEAMS IN BENDING

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1 Introduction

Recently, parts of sandwich and composite materials are more frequently used for construction and production of land transport vehicles. An example of sandwich materials application is manufacturing of self-contained shells of land transport. Phenolic, unsaturated polyester and epoxy resins are used as matrix, glass, carbon and aramid fibers are applied as reinforcement in these application. Sandwich material used for construction of land transport vehicles must match a lot of requirements. Material should be resistant to mechanical failure and fire. For designing and dimensioning sandwich composite parts is important to know data of components and mechanical properties of whole sandwich materials. Mechanical properties of sandwich are usually determined by means of tensile test and bend test of skins (bearing layers), and by means of compression test and shear test of core. In time of sandwich parts design of trolley car the mechanical data were required. An alternative test to ASTM D7250 with skins with different thicknesses and mechanical properties is proposed.

2 Testing of Sandwich Beams

2.1 Material

Testing samples have been taken from sandwich plate made in Variel, a.s., Zruč nad Sázavou (Czech Republic). Sandwich plate had dimension 1000 x 1000 mm. Inside and outside skins of total thickness 3.4 and 4.2 mm respectively were made-up from gelcoat NUVOPOL 80-51JPG (W. Mäder A.G. Kilwangen) with theoretical thickness 0.5 mm, one surfacing mat CO-BACK W 50g/cm² (Akzo Nobel Fibers NL-Amhen). Inside and outside skin of sandwich shell was made-up from four layers of woven fabric 624 g/m² (Saertex A.H. Meyer Zürich)

(0° 240 g/m², 90° 372 g/m², total 624 g/m²) and UP resin NUVOPOL 80-05 G (W. Mäder A.G. Kilwangen). PVC foam core was made-up from HEREX C 70.55.

2.2 Loading

Mechanical tests of sandwich beams without ribs were made in servo hydraulic testing machine INSTRON 1273 (± 100 kN dynamic load, 200 kN static load) with hydraulic jaws. Measured data from testing machine were recorded by central measurement system Hewlett-Packard 3852. Software package LabWindows 5.1 (National Instruments) and self measuring program were used for logging and data evaluation.

Testing beam elements for bending test were cut from sandwich plate in two directions. Five pieces were cut in peripheral direction of winding and five elements were cut in axial direction of self-contained shells. Length of tested beam elements was 500 mm, specimen width was 100 ± 0.1 mm and thickness 50 ± 0.1 mm. Measurement method and data evaluation of bending test was made by standard ASTM C-393 [6]. Testing beam element was loaded in middle of the support span. Span of support was 400 mm. Displacement velocity was $5 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. In the course of test outside skin of sandwich beam was located up. Surrounding temperature in the course of test was 23 ± 2 °C.

Testing machines Hewlett-Packard 3852 recorded all data including forces, middle deflection, acting force and vertical deflection. Deflection was measured by two LVDT sensors at both sides of sandwich beam in the middle. Measured data were plotted into diagram of loading forces on beam deflection. Maximum value of beam deflection and maximum value of force at failure was getting from this bending diagram. Bending test results of sandwich in peripheral are shown in fig. 1 and in table 1.

Bending test results in axial direction shown in fig. 2 and in table 2.

Nonlinear relations load – vertical displacement was obtained from tests in bending of peripheral and axial direction winding specimens and the curves was approximated by polynomial interpolation (fig. 1,2).

Fig.1 Load-displacement curve , Direction x

Fig.2 Load-displacement curve, Direction y

2.3 Comparative Core Shear Modulus

Vertical displacement for three point sandwich beam bending is

$$w = \frac{P_1 l^3}{48C_3 b} \left(1 + 12 \frac{C_2}{Bl^2} \right)$$

and stresses are

$$\sigma_H = E_H h_H \frac{P_1 l}{4bC_3}$$

$$\sigma_D = -E_D h_D \frac{P_1 l}{4bC_3}$$

Applying the equations we obtain a relationship for comparative shear modulus

$$G_C = \frac{18P_1 C_2}{(48C_3 u b - P_1 l^3)(t_H + 3s + t_D)}$$

In above equations the following values are:

$$\delta = -\frac{E_H t_H (t_H + 2s) - E_D t_D (t_D + 2s)}{2(E_H t_H + 2E_C s + E_D t_D)}$$

$$h_H = t_H + s + \delta = t_H + s_H$$

$$h_D = t_D + s - \delta = t_D + s_D$$

$$C_2 = E_H t_H s_H \left(s_H + \frac{1}{2} t_H \right) + \frac{1}{3} E_C (s_H^3 + s_D^3) + E_D t_D s_D \left(s_D + \frac{1}{2} t_D \right)$$

$$C_3 = E_H t_H \left[s_H (s_H + t_H) + \frac{1}{3} t_H^2 \right] + \frac{1}{3} E_C (s_H^3 + s_D^3) + E_D t_D \left[s_D (s_D + t_D) + \frac{1}{3} t_D^2 \right]$$

$$B = \frac{2}{3} G_C (t_H + 3s + t_D)$$

2.3 Calculation of Comparative Core Shear Modulus

The comparative shear modules were calculated for both directions (axial and hoop) according to manufacturing and various loads and displacements, e.g. for direction x and y, load $P_1=5\text{kN}$ and $u=10.6\text{ mm}$ are shear modules

$$\underline{\underline{G_C = 9.5715 \text{ MPa}}}$$

$$\underline{\underline{G_C = 9.8157 \text{ MPa}}}$$

References

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